

Causal Discovery

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1 Introduction

Causal inference has become widely popular and a powerful tool in machine learning. At the heart of any machine learning model are some assumptions about the data generating process. Naively, one assumes the features that *determine* an outcome are uncorrelated. When linearity is used as a further simplifying assumption this gives rise to linear regression models, moreover, even at the nonlinear level such as *neural networks*, an arbitrary choice of the network structure does not take into account the dependencies that might exist within feature variables. Graphical structures provide a natural way to encode dependencies that exist in a multivariate probability distribution. The properties of the graph \mathcal{G} that represents a probability distribution \mathcal{P} are directly related to the dependencies that exist among the random variables. These graphical models are often called *bayesian networks* (BN) or *probabilistic graphical models*.

Given a probability distribution \mathcal{P} *causal graphs* (CG) are a subset of the *bayesian networks* where the directional arrows are given a much stronger *causal semantics*. That is in a *causal graph* $A \rightarrow B$ is interpreted as A causes B , that is a stronger claim in addition to the fact that A, B as random variables are dependent.

In this report we will be exploring ways in which CG can be recovered from observational data to the extent possible or a simpler causal claim, A causes B is validated or assigned a degree of confidence. In general causal discovery algorithms fall into three distinct categories,

- Constraint Based Methods
- Score Based Methods
- Bayesian Averaging Methods

2 Constraint Based Approaches

Constraint based methods are built on top of an *oracle* that validates conditional independence queries such as “Is X independent of Y given Z ?”. Here X, Y, Z are random variables and the query is expressed using the following notation $X \perp Y | Z$. This basic query is often termed *hypothesis testing*. Here we describe the paradigm for independence test by illustrating a commonly used test known as χ^2 -test.

2.1 Independence Test

Let \mathcal{H}_0 be a null hypothesis then given observational data \mathcal{D} a *deviance measure* d is a function from the space of all possible datasets to reals. The number assigned by this function is a measure of how different a dataset is from the null hypothesis \mathcal{H}_0 . Of relevance to causal discovery are hypotheses of the form $\mathcal{H}_0 = X \perp Y | Z$. We examine two commonly used deviance measures frequently termed χ^2 -statistic and *mutual information*, based on empirical distribution \hat{P} defined by data \mathcal{D} .

Consider a set of random-variables X, Y, Z and a dataset \mathcal{D} that was generated by the marginal $P(X, Y, Z)$. If we denote the number of samples where $X = x, Y = y, Z = z$ by $\mathbf{N}(x, y, z)$ and other combinations similarly, it is easy to see that the empirical probabilities \hat{P} can be evaluated as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{P}(x) &= \frac{\mathbf{N}(x)}{\mathbf{N}} && \text{Here } \mathbf{N} \text{ denotes the total number of samples} \\ \hat{P}(x, y) &= \frac{\mathbf{N}(x, y)}{\mathbf{N}} \\ \hat{P}(x, y|z) &= \frac{\mathbf{N}(x, y, z)}{\mathbf{N}(z)}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

To be concrete let us consider the validation of the query $X \perp Y|Z$. The *deviance measure* based on the χ^2 -statistic is given by

$$d_{\chi^2}(\mathcal{D}) = \sum_{x, y, z} \frac{(\mathbf{N}(x, y, z) - \mathbf{N}\hat{P}(z)P(x|z)\hat{P}(y|z))^2}{\mathbf{N}\hat{P}(z)P(x|z)\hat{P}(y|z)}\tag{2}$$

A similar measure termed *mutual information* of the empirical distribution for the above query is given by

$$d_I(\mathcal{D}) = I_{\hat{P}}(X; Y|Z) = \sum_z \hat{P}(z) \sum_y \sum_x \hat{P}(x, y|z) \log \frac{\hat{P}(x, y|z)}{\hat{P}(x|z)\hat{P}(y|z)}\tag{3}$$

2.2 Constrained based algorithm from an *independence oracle*

Here we turn to the problem of determining structure from data to the extent possible. The methods presented here will depend on an *Oracle* capable of determining independence queries such as $X \perp Y|Z$. In order to explain these algorithms we first discuss some formal preliminaries involving characterizations of DAGs.

Definition 2.1. I-Map

Given a dag \mathcal{G} it is associated with the following *local independencies* denoted $\mathcal{I}_l(\mathcal{G})$

$$\mathcal{I}_l(\mathcal{G}) = \{X \perp N_X | P_A(X)\} \quad \forall X \in \mathcal{G}\tag{4}$$

Here $P_A(X)$ are the parents of X and N_X are the set of non-descendants of X . So this essentially states that conditioned on the parents of X , X is independent of all its non-descendants. \mathcal{G} is an **I-map** of a given distribution P if $\mathcal{I}_l(\mathcal{G})$ is a subset of set of independencies in the distribution denoted, $\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{P})$ i.e., $\mathcal{I}_l(\mathcal{G}) \subset \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{P})$

Definition 2.2. P-Map

A DAG \mathcal{G} is a **P-Map** or *perfect map* for P if and only if the set of all *global independencies* induced from $\mathcal{I}_l(\mathcal{G})$ denoted $\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{G}) = \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{P})$

Definition 2.3. I-equivalence

Two different maps \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 are **I-Equivalent** if and only if $\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{G}_1) = \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{G}_2)$

2.2.1 Identifying the *I-equivalence class*

Two graphs $\mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2$ are necessarily different if their *skeleton*, the graph that remains when removing the direction in the edges, is different i.e., $\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{G})_1 \neq \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{G})_2$. It is clear that without any human domain expertise we could only hope to find the *equivalence class* of graphs determined by the *I-equivalence* relation, by using the data alone. One of the maps in this I-equivalence class will be the *causal graph* and the properties that are common among all the graphs in the *equivalence class* will be shared by

the causal diagram it self. If there is a directed edge $X \rightarrow Y$ exists in all the graphs in the *equivalence* class representing a given data \mathcal{D} then it exists in the *causal diagram* too. Given the importance of the *equivalence class*, It is useful to have an economical representation of it. The following theorem furnishes such representation

Theorem 2.4. *Two graphs $\mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2$ are I-Equivalent if and only if they share the same skeleton and the same set of naked colliders of the form $X \rightarrow Y \leftarrow Z$ without any **direct edge** between X, Z .*

Guided by this theorem our method for finding the *I-equivalence* class supporting a given dataset \mathcal{D} is made of two steps,

1. Generating the *skeleton* \mathcal{S}
2. Finding the *naked colliders* of the form stated in the theorem

2.2.1.1 Generating the *skeleton*

If X, Y are adjacent in a graph then they are dependent conditioned on any possible set of nodes \mathbf{U} , that is we expect all conditional independence queries to fail. Conversely, if X, Y are **not** adjacent then there exists a set of nodes \mathbf{U} such that $X \perp Y | \mathbf{U}$. The following theorems make these statements precise.

Theorem 2.5. *Let \mathcal{G} be a P-map of a distribution P , and let X and Y be two variables such that $X \rightarrow Y$ is in \mathcal{G} . Then, $X \perp Y | \mathbf{U} \notin \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{G})$ for any subset \mathbf{U} .*

Theorem 2.6. *Let \mathcal{G} be a P-map of a distribution P , and let X and Y be two variables such that there is no direct edge between them. Then either $X \perp Y | P_A(X)$ or $X \perp Y | P_A(Y)$.*

Armed with these theorems we now explicate an algorithm that generates a *skeleton* corresponding to a distribution P and consequently to a dataset \mathcal{D} generated by it.

Consider a set of random variables $\mathcal{X} = \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$ and a *complete* undirected graph \mathcal{S} over \mathcal{X} , that has an undirected edge between every pair $(X_i, X_j) \in \mathcal{X}$. We investigate each pair (X_i, X_j) in turn and test for independence given any set $\mathbf{U} \subset \mathcal{P}_{(X_i, X_j)} = (\mathcal{N}_b(X_i) - \{X_j\}) \cup (\mathcal{N}_b(X_j) - \{X_i\})$. It is clear that $\mathcal{P}_{(X_i, X_j)}$ is the superset containing any potential subsets that can separate X_i, X_j . If we find such a subset U we remove the edge between X and Y and record the subset U . If we fail to find any subset we move on to another pair of variables. It can be shown that this procedure converges to a unique skeleton. If we make a simplifying assumption that the maximum number of inbound arrows to any node is d , the time complexity of these method is $\mathcal{O}(n^{(d+2)})$.

2.2.2 Finding the *naked colliders* given a *skeleton*

Given that we have found a skeleton \mathcal{S} supporting a distribution $P(\mathcal{X})$ what remains to be done is to find all *naked colliders* in the skeleton \mathcal{S} . The following theorem furnishes a procedure to find such *nakedcolliders*.

Theorem 2.7. *Suppose $X - Z - Y \in \mathcal{S}$ and let X, Y have no direct edges. Then, $X - Z - Y$ is a naked collider, $X \rightarrow Z \leftarrow Y$ if and only if for any U that satisfies $X \perp Y | U$, $Z \notin U$.*

Proof. Suppose there exists a $U \ni Z$ such that $X \perp Y | U$ then there cannot be a trail such as $X \rightarrow Z \leftarrow Y$ since in this case conditioned on Z , X and Y are dependent. Conversely suppose for any U such that $X \perp Y | U$, $Z \notin U$. Then, there cannot be any trails of the form $X \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$ or $X \leftarrow Z \rightarrow Y$ since when **not conditioned** on Z both of these trails are active, that is X and Y are dependent. \square

Armed with this theorem the problem of finding the *naked colliders* is a triviality. We simply check given *potential naked collider* $X - Z - Y \in \mathcal{S}$ whether Z is contained in the set U that is returned by the previous algorithm (2.2.1.1) that satisfied $X \perp Y|U$ given the pair X, Y . With the two algorithms (2.2.1.1) and (2.2.1.1) we have completed our goal of finding both criteria that characterizes an *I-equivalence* class. Namely, the *skeleton* and all *naked colliders*.

The utility of this approach for *causal discovery* is based on the fact that any directed edge that exists via the above characterisation of the *I-equivalence class* also exists in the causal diagram which is a special member of this *I-equivalence class*.

2.2.3 Limitations of the constraint based algorithm

3 Score based methods

Score based methods approach the problem of structure learning within an optimization framework. In this formulation we assign an appropriate score for a given graph \mathcal{G} and data-set \mathcal{D} . One of the most important factors that drive the methodology in this approach is the choice of scores to attribute to a graph \mathcal{G} and data \mathcal{D} . Two of the natural choices frequently used are,

- Likelihood Score denoted: $score_L(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D})$
- Bayesian Score denoted: $score_B(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D})$

3.1 Likelihood Score

It can be shown the probability distribution P characterized by a network G factorises in the following way,

Theorem 3.1. *If \mathcal{G} is an I-Map for P over a set of random variables $\mathcal{X} = \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$ then, P factorises as*

$$P(X_1, \dots, X_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(X_i | P_A(X_i)) \quad (5)$$

Notice that the marginal distribution is expressed as a product of individual conditional probability distributions, $P(X_i | P_A(X_i))$.

The above result points to a natural way to express the maximum likelihood estimate associated with a graph \mathcal{G} . Suppose we impose a conditional probability distribution or density associated to each factor appearing in (5) that depends on a set of parameters $\theta_{(X_i | P_A(X_i))}$. Note that if P is a discrete distribution then each $\theta_{[x_i | P_A(x_i)]}$, $x_i \in Val(X_i)$, $P_A(x_i) \in Val(P_A(X_i))$ can be taken to be the probability of having the realization $X_i = x_i$ given $P_A(X_i) = P_A(x_i)$. In the case of continuous variables $\theta_{[x_i | P_A(x_i)]}$ are parameters defining the density function of a given distribution such as Gaussian, beta etc. Now given a dataset \mathcal{D} consisting of N iid samples over the n random variables, we can write the likelihood associated with this data given parameter $\theta_{\mathcal{G}}$ is given by,

$$L(\theta_{\mathcal{G}} : \mathcal{D}) = \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^n P(x_j^i | P_A(x_j^i); \theta_{[x_j^i | P_A(x_j^i)]}) \quad (6)$$

Here x_j^i is the realized value of the random variable X_j in the i^{th} sample point of \mathcal{D} and $P_A(x_j^i)$ is the vector of values taken by the parents of X_j in the i^{th} sample. Clearly, (6) implies the following decomposition for the maximum log-likelihood score of network \mathcal{G} and data \mathcal{D}

$$\mathbf{score}_L(\mathcal{G} : \hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}}) := l(\hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}} : \mathcal{D}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{FamScore}(X_i | P_A(X_i) : \mathcal{D}) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{FamScore}(X_i | P_A(X_i) : \mathcal{D}) = \sum_{j=1}^N \ln P(x_i^j | P_A(x_i^j); \hat{\theta}_{[x_j | P_A(x_j^j)]}) \quad (8)$$

Here the *hatted* symbols $\hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\hat{\theta}_{[x_j | P_A(x_j^i)]}$ are the parameters that maximize the log-likelihood. Also note that $\hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \hat{\theta}_{[x_j | P_A(x_j^i)]}$

The above decomposition is over individual *family scores* associated with each node X_i and its parents. *Family score measures* how good the choice of parents of X_i is given the data \mathcal{D} .

3.1.1 Limitations of Likelihood Score

It can be shown that the likelihood score can be represented in the following forms involving *mutual information* and *entropy*. Let $\mathbf{score}(\mathcal{G} : \hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be the maximum likelihood score associated with graph \mathcal{G} and data \mathcal{D} with sample size of N then,

$$\mathbf{score}(\mathcal{G} : \hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}}) = N \sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbb{I}_{\hat{P}}(X_i; P_A(X_i)) - \mathbb{H}_{\hat{P}}(X_i)) \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{score}(\mathcal{G} : \hat{\theta}_{\mathcal{G}}) = N \left[\mathbb{H}_{\hat{P}}(X_1, \dots, X_n) - \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{I}_{\hat{P}}(X_i; \{X_1, \dots, X_{i-1}\} - P_A(X_i)) \right] \quad (10)$$

Here in the second expression the random variables are given an ordering such that, X_1, \dots, X_n is a topological ordering for the given graph \mathcal{G} . Moreover, $\mathbb{H}_{\hat{P}}$ and $\mathbb{I}_{\hat{P}}$ denote the *entropy* and *mutual information* computed using the sample distribution \hat{P} . We can interpret the first expression (9) as measuring the extent to which the parent nodes $P_A(X_i)$ determine X_i . The second term in the expression (10) computes the mutual information between X_i and its ancestors that are not parents. This can be interpreted to mean that (10) measures how much the data deviates from the independence property asserted by the graph \mathcal{G} . For any subsets of random variables \mathbf{X} , \mathbf{Y} and \mathbf{Z} we have,

$$\mathbb{I}(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Y} \cup \mathbf{Z}) \geq \mathbb{I}(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Y}) \quad (11)$$

since the information about \mathbf{X} increases as we add more variables. We can clearly see from the first term in (9) that the likelihood score will increase as the size of the parent set increases which subsequently increases the complexity of the network. This causes the likelihood score to prefer more complex networks, the most complex being the *complete graph*. Such dense graphs give scarce information about the independencies in the random variables. This tendency to over-fit is the major limitation of the structure learning using maximum likelihood score. To alleviate this problem one can introduce constraints that limits the complexity of the network, such as setting the maximum bound for the *indegree* (the number of parents of a node)

3.2 Bayesian Score

In this section we discuss a score based on Bayesian perspective. Bayesian score overcomes the problem of over-fitting by means of regularisation as we discuss later. The central principle in Bayesian framework is that we associate a prior distribution for anything we are uncertain about. Given a Bayesian network \mathcal{G} , data \mathcal{D} and a set of parameters associated with the graph $\theta_{\mathcal{G}}$ we seek to estimate the *posterior* probability of the DAG \mathcal{G} given data. Namely,

$$P(\mathcal{G} | \mathcal{D}) = \frac{P(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{G}) P(\mathcal{G})}{P(\mathcal{D})} \quad (12)$$

The denominator $P(\mathcal{D})$ is only a normalising constant and does not depend on our choice of network \mathcal{G} . $P(\mathcal{G})$ is the *prior* over a set of network structures, representing our belief about each structure \mathcal{G} . Neglecting the $P(\mathcal{D})$, the Bayesian score is defined as,

$$\mathbf{score}_B(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D}) = \ln P(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{G}) + \ln P(\mathcal{G}) \quad (13)$$

Here the second term involving the parameter prior $P(\mathcal{G})$ serves as a regularisation for the complexity of the network. It is clearly seen that the Bayesian score takes into account the uncertainty over the parameters given a network structure $P(\theta_{\mathcal{G}}|\mathcal{G})$. Indeed,

$$P(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{G}) = \int d\theta_{\mathcal{G}} P(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{G}, \theta_{\mathcal{G}}) P(\theta_{\mathcal{G}}|\mathcal{G}) \quad (14)$$

In order to consider the decomposition property of the Bayesian score, we use the factorisation over the network \mathcal{G} as mentioned in 5. We first demand that an appropriate choice of the the prior considers only the local CPD's associated with the graph. To be precise we assume that,

$$P(\theta_{\mathcal{G}}|\mathcal{G}) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(\theta_{X_i|P_A(X_i)}|\mathcal{G}) \quad (15)$$

Given a iid dataset \mathcal{D} of size N and denoting the i^{th} instantiation as $\mathcal{X}[i]$ and similarly denoting the value taken by random variable X_j at the i^{th} sample as $X_j[i]$, we can write,

$$P(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{G}, \theta_{\mathcal{G}}) = \prod_{i=1}^N P(\mathcal{X}[i]|\mathcal{G}, \theta_{\mathcal{G}}) \quad (16)$$

$$P(\mathcal{X}[i]|\mathcal{G}, \theta_{\mathcal{G}}) = \prod_{j=1}^n P(X_j[i]|P_A(X_j), \theta_{X_j|P_A(X_j)}) \quad (17)$$

Hence (16) becomes,

$$P(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{G}, \theta_{\mathcal{G}}) = \prod_{i=1}^N \left[\prod_{j=1}^n [P(X_j[i]|P_A(X_j), \theta_{X_j|P_A(X_j)})] \right] \quad (18)$$

Interchanging the products and assuming *global parameter separation*, $\theta_{X_j|P_A(X_j)} \cap \theta_{X_i|P_A(X_i)} = \emptyset$ when $i \neq j$, it follows from (15), (18),

$$\ln P(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{G}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{FamScore}(X_i|P_A(X_i) : \mathcal{D}) \quad (19)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{FamScore}(X_i|P_A(X_i) : \mathcal{D}) = \int d\theta_{X_j|P_A(X_j)} \prod_{j=1}^n \ln P(X_j[i]|P_A(X_j), \theta_{X_j|P_A(X_j)}) \quad (20)$$

Thus we see that the Bayesian score similar to Likelihood score allows the following decomposition,

$$\mathbf{score}_B(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{FamScore}(X_i|P_A(X_i) : \mathcal{D}) + \ln P(\mathcal{G}) \quad (21)$$

Note that $P(\mathcal{G})$ is usually negligible compared to the first term. An approximation for the *Bayesian score* is given by *BIC score* (Bayesian Information Criterion)

$$\mathbf{score}_{BIC}(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D}) = l(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D}) - \ln \left(\frac{N}{2} \right) \mathbf{Dim}(\mathcal{G}) \quad (22)$$

Here the second term penalizes more complex networks as a regularizer. $\mathbf{Dim}(\mathcal{G})$ is the number of independent parameters in the network \mathcal{G} . So far we have described how to assign *scores* to Bayesian networks given a dataset \mathcal{D} generated by an unknown probability distribution.

3.3 Structure Search

What we now need for structure/causal discovery is a search procedure. Given n random variables, \mathcal{X} the total number of possible DAGs, $G(n)$, is *super exponential*

$$G(n) = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{(k+1)} \binom{n}{k} 2^{k(n-k)} G(n-k) \quad (23)$$

Even for small values for number of nodes, $G(n)$ becomes very large very quickly. For example, $G(8) = 783702329343$. Thus it is a hopeless task to search the entire *search space* and we resort to some *heuristic* search procedures that constrains the size of the search space. This limitation of the *search space* can be informed by human understanding of the probable structures.

3.3.1 Characterization of the search space

Search space of probable DAG's can be thought of as a graph itself where each node represents a DAG. The connections between these graphs is usually an *legal* operation that changes the graph. If the number of neighbors of a given DAG \mathcal{G} is large then the search procedure has to spend more time evaluating the score of each neighbor. On the other hand, having relatively few neighbours can make the search path long, i.e, it may take a longer trail to traverse from a given graph \mathcal{G}_1 to the optimal graph \mathcal{G}^* . In order to manage this trade-off a *heuristic search procedure* is widely used, where the *operations*, \mathcal{O} that can be performed is restricted to the following

- Edge Addition
- Edge Deletion
- Edge Reversal

Given the number of nodes, n , there can at most be $2 \times \binom{n}{2}$ edges. Hence the *diameter* of any *search procedure* employing the above operators are restricted to be less $\binom{n}{2}$, i.e to go from \mathcal{G}_1 to \mathcal{G}_2 one can delete all the edges that are in \mathcal{G}_1 and not in \mathcal{G}_2 and *vice versa*, thus this operation is bounded by the total number of edges that can be.

3.3.2 A heuristic search procedure

A widely used search procedure starts at a DAG \mathcal{G}_1 which is chosen either randomly or by domain knowledge. Subsequently a *greedy search* is performed evaluating the score of each neighbouring networks whose size is $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. Hence for a trail that involves S steps, $\mathcal{O}(Sn^2)$ operations are performed. For each such operation we have to evaluate the score of the graph reached. To perform this score the algorithm must access each datapoint in \mathcal{D} to compute the necessary statistic which requires a time-complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N)$. Finally the each graph needs to be checked if *acyclicity*. An operation that requires $\mathcal{O}(nd)$ for a network with the bounded indegree of d . Hence time-complexity of this simple search procedure is $\mathcal{O}(Sn^2(N + nd))$. The most expensive operation in this search procedure is the computation of the score for each network. This computation is vastly reduced if we employ a score function that is decomposable into family scores associated to the nodes and their parents as shown in (7), (21). Namely,

$$\text{score}(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{FamScore}(X_i, P_A(X_i)) \quad (24)$$

This decomposition makes the scoring of graphs incremental moving from one graph to another via one of the operations listed in (3.3.1). The following proposition makes this notion precise.

Theorem 3.2. Let \mathcal{G} be a DAG and $o \in \mathcal{O}$ be a given operator. If we define the change in score going from \mathcal{G} to $\mathcal{G}' := o(\mathcal{G})$ as

$$\delta(\mathcal{G}, o) = \mathbf{score}(o(\mathcal{G}) : \mathcal{D}) - \mathbf{score}(\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{D}) \quad (25)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} o = \text{Add edge } X \rightarrow Y \text{ and } X \rightarrow Y \notin \mathcal{G} &\implies \delta(\mathcal{G}, o) = \mathbf{FamScore}(Y, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(Y) \cup X) - \mathbf{FamScore}(Y, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(Y)) \\ o = \text{Delete edge } X \rightarrow Y \text{ and } X \rightarrow Y \in \mathcal{G} &\implies \delta(\mathcal{G}, o) = \mathbf{FamScore}(Y, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(Y) - \{X\}) - \mathbf{FamScore}(Y, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(Y)) \\ o = \text{Reverse edge } X \rightarrow Y \text{ and } X \rightarrow Y \in \mathcal{G} &\implies \delta(\mathcal{G}, o) = \mathbf{FamScore}(Y, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(Y) \cup X) + \mathbf{FamScore}(X, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(X)) \\ &\quad - \mathbf{FamScore}(Y, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(Y)) - \mathbf{FamScore}(X, P_A^{\mathcal{G}}(X)) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

3.4 Score based search for *Causal Discovery*

Score based methods can be used for *causal discovery*. We note that the *score based* algorithm will find a best scoring DAG \mathcal{G} . However, most probably \mathcal{G} cannot be assigned any *causal semantics*, as the only guarantee we have is that the causal graph \mathcal{G}^c is one of the DAGs in the *I-equivalence class* of \mathcal{G} . Hence we need to a procedure to generate the *I-equivalence class* given a member \mathcal{G} .

3.4.1 Generating the *I-equivalence class* given a member \mathcal{G}

It is convenient to choose an economical representation of the *I-equivalence class* rather than listing all the members, since the size of the *I-equivalence class* can be exponentially large. An effective way to represent it would be to first have the *skeleton* of the class which should be unique for an *I-equivalence class* then mark the directions if and only if all DAGs in the *I-equivalence class* share that directional edge. This would result in a PDAG (Partial DAG) that consists of both directed and undirected edges. Given a DAG \mathcal{G} the skeleton can easily be discerned by replacing directed edges with undirected edges. Moreover one can use the algorithm that was discussed in (2.2.2) to find the *naked colliders*. The directed edges that are part of the *naked colliders* must exist in all the members of the *I-equivalence class* due to theorem (2.4). There may be some additional directed edges that are **not** part of the *naked colliders*, this is due to constraints such as not creating a spurious *naked collider*. It is easy to see that the following rules dictate how additional directed edges in the skeleton. The rules R_1, R_2, R_3 turn out to be sufficient for finding all possible directed edges in the PDAG representation.

Figure 1: Rules determining the additional directed edges

Armed with these rules we can devise the following algorithms that generates a PDAG given a member \mathcal{G}

1. Get the *skeleton* \mathcal{K} from \mathcal{G}
2. $\mathcal{K} \leftarrow$ add the *naked colliders* by using (2.2.2)
3. **While not converged:**
 4. Find a subgraph in \mathcal{K} that matches the left hand side of the rules R_1, R_2, R_3
 5. Replace the subgraph found with one the right hand side of the respective rule
6. **Return** \mathcal{K}

4 Bayesian Averaging

An important limitation of the *score based* approach is that we are committing to a structure that maximises the score relative to data \mathcal{D} . It can be shown that the posterior probability $P(\mathcal{G}^*|\mathcal{D})$ of the correct structure \mathcal{G}^* grows linearly with the data and we can conclude that as $N \rightarrow \infty$ the difference in score of \mathcal{G}^* from other structures. However this asymptotic result does not promise that in the regime where there is much less data our choice of maximum scoring structure is the right one. Adhering to the Bayesian principle one should get an average result weighted on the posterior probability of the structures $P(\mathcal{G}|\mathcal{D})$. Suppose we are testing for a certain numeric feature of the graph $f(\mathcal{G})$, for example, a binary feature that checks whether X, Y are *d-separated* given Z . the Bayesian principle advocates we take the expectation as a measure of confidence

$$E_{P(\mathcal{G}|\mathcal{D})}[f(\mathcal{G})] = \sum_{\mathcal{G}} f(\mathcal{G})P(\mathcal{G}|\mathcal{D}) \quad (27)$$

Notice that the above posterior probability can be computed from the *Bayesian score* we discussed above, more precisely,

$$P(\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{D}) = \exp \left(\sum_i \mathbf{FamScore}(X_i, P_A(X_i)) \right) \quad (28)$$

In practice however, the above sum is *superexponential* as we discussed earlier. So a practical approach is to use some smaller subset \mathbf{G} of high-scoring structures and approximate (27) as below,

$$E_{P(\mathcal{G}|\mathcal{D})}[f(\mathcal{G})] = \frac{\sum_{\mathcal{G} \in \mathbf{G}} P(\mathcal{G}|\mathcal{D})f(\mathcal{G})}{\sum_{\mathcal{G} \in \mathbf{G}} P(\mathcal{G}|\mathcal{D})} \quad (29)$$

The utility of *Bayesian averaging* is particularly suited to *causal discovery*. Given a prior $P(\mathcal{G})$ over a candidate set of causal structures (27) gives a *confidence score* over any queries that we may have such as, “Does X cause Y ?”.